

THE WESTERN-EASTERN NATURE OF ARTISTIC CONSCIOUSNESS CHINGIZ AITMATOV

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Abstract: the article examines the writer's works, their psychological and artistic structure, and shows good and evil - intertwined with national problems with different perceptions of moral and spiritual values and laws

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Chingiz Torekulovich Aitmatov (1928-2008) was a bilingual Kyrgyz prose writer who wrote in two languages: Kyrgyz and Russian. The writer spent almost his entire childhood with his grandmother, his first impressions of life are associated with national Kyrgyz colour. The family spoke both Kyrgyz and Russian, which determined the bilingual nature of Aitmatov's work.

Until 1965 Aitmatov wrote in Kyrgyz. The first story he wrote in Russian was Farewell, Gulsary! The fate of the protagonist, the Kyrgyz peasant Tananbai, is as typical as the fates of the best heroes of "village prose". Tananbai took part in collectivisation without sparing his own brother, and then fell victim to the Party's careerists. The image of Gulsary that accompanied Tananbai for many years played an important role in the story. Critics have noted that Gulsary's image is a metaphor for the essence of human life, in which the suppression of personality and rejection of the naturalness of existence are inevitable. G. Gachev described Gulsary as Aitmatov's characteristic "two-headed centaur image" of animal and human.[1]

Aitmatov created wonderful works within the framework of the novel. In the story, the writer turns to folklore. The myth present in the work fulfils a dual function: an ideological and aesthetic one and a national one. Myth for Aitmatov is a "ball of wisdom" of the ancients, an experience tested by generations. Myth modulates the artistic view of the world; it becomes a tool for discovering the urgent problems of the present day and penetrating into the depths of public reason. Following the example of myth, the artist depicts social relations, making philosophical sense of them.[2]

The next work we want to talk about, which caused much controversy in criticism among many readers, was Aitmatov's second novel The Plakha (1986). It shows the civic courage characteristic of Aitmatov as a writer, as well as a

sense of the new social and spiritual trends of the time. To date, one of the social and moral problems touched upon in this work - the problem of drug addiction - remains central.

The plot of the novel consists of three almost unrelated lines. The action takes place in the second half of the 1980s in Central Asia, on Issyk-Kul, the writer's second homeland; in Russia, in Moscow and on the Oka River.

The protagonist of the first storyline is Avdi Kallistratov, a student at a theological seminary and a journalist who afterwards collects a particularly significant material on drug addicts and drug addiction. The novel vividly reveals Avdi Kallistratov's moral and religious quest, which accurately reflects one of the trends in society. In creating the image of this character, Aitmatov follows the traditions of the Russian classics and acts as an orientalist author in doing so.

The Eastern literary tradition allows the creation of new texts on the plot of a classical work with the obligatory use of size, rhyme and the system of tropes of the work to which a representative of a new literary generation responds with his creation. However, the nature of Aitmatov's artistic consciousness is dual - Western-Eastern. That is why he chose as a high example the work of a Russian writer, the novel *Master and Margarita* by M. Bulgakov.[3] This resulted in a kind of "Western-Eastern" synthesis: the Gospel chapters of Bulgakov's novel, like the Gospel itself, were the "material" on which the Kirghiz writer embroidered his original "ornaments". But one cannot accept the critic's reproach that Aitmatov allegedly abdicated his nationality, religion and culture in the name of cosmopolitanism that overwhelmed him and rewrote the Bible and Mikhail Bulgakov's novel in "Plakha". Any writer, irrespective of his religion, has the right to refer to the Bible and *The Master and Margarita* in the performance of a certain creative task. In this case, the Gospel chapters of Bulgakov's novel, as well as the Gospel itself, were the "canvas" on which the Kyrgyz writer embroidered his original "patterns".

The second storyline of *The Plakha* relates to the era of the birth of Christianity. The heroes of this line are Jesus Christ and Pontius Pilate. In some ways Aitmatov is very close to Bulgakov, but at the same time very different from him

Unlike Bulgakov, Aitmatov introduced additional characters - the Mother of God and God the Father. The scene of acknowledgement of the little Jesus by God-the-Father is important for revealing the image of Aitmatov's Christ. Firstly, this reveals the writer who grew up in Central Asia's respect for his parents.

Second, Aitmatov, unlike Bulgakov, emphasizes not only the earthly but also the divine nature of God the Son. [4]

The third subject line in "Plakhi" is connected to material that is well known and familiar to Aitmatov - the life and work of a Kyrgyz shepherd Boston Urkunchiev, who is not indifferent to his work and to everything that goes on around him. Boston, like Avdi, is a hero of a transitional type (a progressive shepherd, at the height of socialism he calls for the land and livestock to be given to the shepherds). He is close to the "soil" old men and old women of the Russian "rustlers": Boston is a great toiler, an exemplary family man.

The three storylines of the work are linked to the story of the death of a pair of wolves - Tashchaynar, his blue-eyed wolf Akbara and their "hapless wolf cubs". The lyricism and poetry of the novel is given by Akbara's lamentations that go back to Kyrgyz folklore lamentations. There is a kind of allegory of modern humanity's extermination of nature and its revenge on it.[5]

The different storylines of the novel highlight the types of predatory or conformist heroes (Grishan, Ober-Kandalov, Bazarbai Noygutov, Pontius Pilate) and the hero who is prepared to die in defence of his convictions (Avdi, Jesus Christ, Boston). Unlike the earlier representatives of this type, the drama is intensified in the images of these characters: they either perish themselves or their world perishes as a result of a tragic mistake. The critic E. Surkov is right: "This novel is like a cry. Like a desperate appeal to everyone. To come to their senses. To realize their responsibility. For everything that is so - at the limit - aggravated and condensed in the world.

Aitmatov's works are imbued with the flavour of the life of the people, full of psychology, drama and lyricism. Human destiny, pain, greed and injustice run through most of his novels. This, to an extent, makes Aitmatov's works unforgettable and of interest to a wide circle of readers. For his works, Aitmatov was awarded the highest state prize of the time - more than once.

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